

Moisture Interaction Characteristics and Fracture in Polymer Composites

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ABSTRACT

The effect of water absorption has been investigated on the diffusion behavior and fracture properties of thermoset and thermoplastic polymer matrix composites. The glass transition temperature, T_g , was lowered as a result of moisture uptake. However, T_g recovers upon moisture desorption. The composite materials were submerged in distilled water at temperatures from 318 K (45°C) to 363 K (90°C) for more than 9000 h. Moisture saturation levels were considerably higher in the thermoset composites than in the thermoplastic composite. Water sorption in the graphite/epoxy composite exhibited both classical Fickian and non-Fickian diffusion behavior. Non-Fickian behavior was related to chemical modification and physical damage in the composite. Moisture sorption in thermoplastic polymer composites follows Fickian diffusion rather closely. Sorbed water lowered the delamination fracture toughness (DFT) of T300/934 thermoset composite whereas moisture sorption had virtually no effect on the DFT of IM6/PEEK thermoplastic composite.

Keywords: water interaction, moisture absorption, polymer composite, fracture, delamination, toughness, glass transition temperature

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Absorbants in polymer matrix composites affect the physical and mechanical properties of PMCs [1-6]. Absorbants such as solvents, liquids, or vapors are absorbed in the bulk matrix phase and at the interface causing degradation. In thermoset (epoxy) composites, sorbed moisture changes the strength, stiffness, and fracture behavior [5,7-12]. Moisture diffusion in PMCs plasticizes the composite materials causing softening, glass transition temperature, T_g , reduction, and swelling of the matrix phase. Sorbed moisture tends to adversely affect the *transverse* mechanical properties of composites, which are controlled by the characteristics of the matrix. Customarily, thermosetting polymer composites (epoxy matrix composites) absorb considerably more water and the associated changes in mechanical and fracture properties are commensurate with the ancillary water gain. In contrast, however, thermoplastic composites (PEEK, polyether-etherketone) matrix composites absorb much less water, and, consequently, no significant effect of moisture is observed on either longitudinal or transverse mechanical properties.

The rate of moisture sorption and the solubility (saturation) limit are influenced primarily by the matrix phase chemistry, and by the physical integrity and composition fiber/matrix interface phase. The moisture saturation level can be 10 times higher in thermoset PMCs in comparison to thermoplastic PMCs. Moisture-related property degradation is associated with the water-matrix interaction characteristics. The nature of the water interaction with the polymer matrix is both chemical and physical. In addition, defects such as void, cracks, and other microstructural inhomogeneities in the bulk matrix and at the fiber/matrix interface contribute to severity of moisture effects in polymer matrix composites [6]. The extent of free volume also plays a role in the resultant behavior of water-laden polymer composites. The deleterious effects of moisture on static properties (strength and stiffness) of PMCs are well documented. However,

published research emphasizing the effects of moisture on fracture and crack propagation behavior is not as prevalent. Because composites are being used in many critical applications, extensive characterization is warranted regarding the effect of the environment, particularly moisture, on fracture properties. In this study, moisture absorption behavior in PMCs is investigated. Damage, delamination fracture, and microcracking processes are examined for graphite/thermoset and graphite-thermoplastic laminate composite systems.

2.0 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

The thermoset composite material investigated was a continuous carbon fiber reinforced epoxy (Gr/Ep) laminate, T300/934, supplied by the ICI Fiberite Company. The nominal cure temperature of T300/934 composites is 177 °C (450 K). The laminate layup consisted of unidirectional [0₁₈] fibers and the fiber volume fraction was 66 percent. The laminate thickness was 2.4 mm. T300/934 carbon fiber-epoxy composite system exhibits brittle fracture behavior and its fracture toughness is typically 5 times lower than the fracture toughness thermoplastic composite materials.

The thermoplastic composite laminate investigated, IM6/PEEK, was 24 plies thick, [0]₂₄. The laminate was fabricated from unidirectional prepreg, IM6/PEEK. The axial fiber modulus (E_{11}) was 280 GPa. The fiber volume fraction was 60 percent. Hybrid test panels were fabricated by adhesive bonding of 6061 aluminum adherends to the IM6/PEEK composite laminate using a heated hydraulic laminating press [11]. Consolidation was achieved by heating the metal-laminate configuration at 393 °C (666 K) under pressure at 0.49 MPa (70 psi) for 8×10^2 seconds. The processing cycle was completed by increasing the pressure to 1.4 MPa (200 psi) for 1.8×10^3 seconds.

2.2 Moisture Absorption

The Gr/Ep and Gr/Ep laminates were saturated with moisture using a hygrothermal absorption technique. Laminate coupons were submerged in a constant-temperature water bath at 45 °C (318 K), 60 °C (333 K), 75 °C (348 K) and 90 °C (363 K). Moisture absorption characteristics for all composites obeyed Fickian diffusion behavior except at the onset of physical damage and/or material degradation. Moisture sorption and diffusion parameters were determined by gravimetric measurements. PMC coupons were weighed periodically using an electronic microbalance with 0.01 mg resolution. In the early stages of moisture sorption, the weight gain (water uptake) by the laminates was linear according to the \sqrt{t} time, and, thus demonstrated Fickian diffusion behavior. Generally, the moisture saturation level in graphite epoxy composites is considerable higher than the saturation moisture level in graphite thermoplastic composites. However, the diffusivity in PEEK composites is greater than in 934-epoxy composites [8,9,11].

2.3 Testing Method

Fracture toughness, K_{Iv} , was determined using a modified chevron notch short bar specimen [12] as describe elsewhere [13]. An appealing aspect of the chevron-notched short bar test is simplicity. Because a sharp crack is initiated at the chevron notch tip, precracking is not essential. Only the maximum load, P_{max} , is needed to determine the fracture toughness provided linear elastic fracture mechanics criteria are satisfied. When P_{max} is reached at a critical crack length, the fracture toughness can be determined. Tests were perform in displacement control on a Fractometer II short bar test system. The grip opening displacement rate was 5.8×10^{-4} mm/s.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Water Diffusion and Matrix Phase Interactions

3.1.1 Diffusion of Water

The diffusion process is similar for both thermoset and thermoplastic polymer matrix composites. Without chemical, physical, or mechanical degradation, Fick's second law describes water diffusion in PMCs [14]. That is,

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \cdot \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2}, \quad (1)$$

where C represents the concentration of the diffusing species, x is a dimensional coordinate, and D is the diffusion coefficient that is temperature dependent. It can be shown that

$$\frac{M_t}{M_m} = \left(\frac{4}{h}\right) \cdot \left[\frac{Dt}{\pi}\right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

by applying suitable boundary conditions. Equation 2 represents the linear segment versus the \sqrt{t} of the moisture sorption profile. Rearranging Eqn. 2, the diffusion coefficient, D, is give by

$$D = \frac{\pi}{16} \left(\frac{h}{M_m}\right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{M_{t_2} - M_{t_1}}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}}\right)^2 \quad (3)$$

The moisture sorbed at time, t, is M_t . M_m is the equilibrium amount of moisture sorbed and h is the laminate thickness. Moreover, the entire moisture-time diffusion profile is determined theoretically by the following expression [5],

$$M_t \approx M_m \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[-7.3 \left(\frac{Dt}{h^2}\right)^{0.75} \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

The diffusion coefficients for T300/934 and IM6/PEEK composites are shown in Table I Fig. 1. From the Fig. 1, diffusion rate as noted by diffusion coefficient and as a function of temperature, D(T), is higher for the thermoplastic polymer composite than for the epoxy polymer matrix composite. Also, the activation energy for diffusion is higher for IM6/PEEK. Diffusion

Diffusivity				
Temperature, K	318	333	348	363
D, m ² /s, (T300/934)	1.13 x 10 ⁻¹³	2.29 x 10 ⁻¹³	5.90 x 10 ⁻¹³	14.5 x 10 ⁻¹³
D, m ² /s, (IM6/PEEK)	2.78 x 10 ⁻¹³	6.29 x 10 ⁻¹³	12.3 x 10 ⁻¹³	29.1 x 10 ⁻¹³

Table I. Temperature Dependent Diffusivity of T300/934 and IM6/PEEK

Fig. 1. Temperature dependent diffusivity and activation energies for T300/934 and IM6/PEEK composites

coefficient values, determined from the initial linear regime of the M_t versus \sqrt{t} diffusion profile, assume that chemical and/or physical damage to the composites is minimal during hygrothermal conditioning. However, when there is moisture-induced damage, the water uptake profile will deviate from classical Fickian diffusion behavior. Fig. 2 shows damage that is often induced by water sorption in carbon epoxy materials. The water-induced damage is manifested by formation

Fig. 2. SEM micrograph of the surface of T300/934 laminate after exposure water for ~ 4000 h at 90 °C. Microcracking damage, leaching, and surface resin dissolution are evident.

of microcracks, resin leaching, and surface dissolution of the composite. The deviation from Fick's law behavior is exhibited in Fig. 3 which shows the experimental and theoretical behavior of water sorption in a carbon fiber-epoxy matrix composite and carbon fiber-thermoplastic

Fig. 3. The moisture absorption profile of T300/934 composite material showing experimental (symbols) and theoretical Fick's law behavior (solid line) at 45, 60, 75 and 90 °C. The dashed lines represent the sorbed moisture saturation level for IM6/PEEK composite laminate.

composite. Water uptake in the PEEK-matrix composite is substantially less than in the epoxy-matrix composite. The dashed lines indicate the saturation level for IM6/PEEK composites.

3.1.2 Water Interaction

3.1.2.1 Infrared Spectra Results

To gain further insight into the nature of water interaction with the polymer matrix, FTIR spectroscopy was conducted. From the infrared, IR, spectra, insight was gained into the nature of chemical interactions of water with the polymer matrix. Fig. 4 shows the IR spectral results dry and hygrothermal-conditioned T300/934 composites. Water tends to interrupt the Van Der Waals bonding of the interchain structure of the polymer. Water interacts with certain hydrophilic

Fig. 4. Infrared spectra of T300/934 composite subjected to various hygrothermal conditions. Note the decrease in 1720 cm^{-1} peak as the severity of the hygrothermal condition increases. Spectra (a) - (e) represent increasing severity of the hygrothermal environment. Spectrum (f) represents a redried specimen by water desorption.

groups, such as hydroxyl and amine groups. A noticeable difference exists between the IR spectra for dry versus water-saturated T300/934 composites. The peak in the IR spectra at 1720 cm^{-1} band gradually decreased with increasing moisture absorption temperatures. This 1720 cm^{-1}

which is associated with the vibration of carbon-oxygen, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, vanishes at high bath temperatures (90 °C) after ~ 9000 h of exposure. The change in the is due to the interaction of the diffusing water with the matrix phase. This contention is supported by the rejuvenation of the 1720 cm^{-1} peak in composite specimens that were redried by water desorption at ~100C. Although not discussed in this study, nuclear magnetic resonance, NMR, data showed significant difference in the chemical environment of free water and absorbed water in the resin matrix composite materials. Such data then will also suggest some change in the bonding character on water as a result of the interaction of water molecules with the resin material.

3.1.2.2 Variation in the T_g

It is well known that the T_g changes with water uptake in the matrix phase of the composite materials. Generally, for every 1-wt% gain in moisture, the T_g is reduced by as much as 10 - 20 degrees depending on the type of material. The data in Table II show that T_g changes significantly with water uptake. Also, the extent of change of T_g depends on the immersion temp-

	Bath Temperature, °C			
	45	60	75	90
T_g , °C Water-saturated @ 9000h	89	102	119	126
T_g , °C Desorbed @ 60 °C for 1250 h	182	183	182	188
T_g , °C Desorbed @ 60°C for 1250 h + desorption @ 100 °C for 250 h	174	175	175	174
T_g , °C As-received - (dry)	175			

Table II. T_g variation with immersion bath temperature and moisture desorption.

Fig. 5 The effects of bath temperature on T_g variation. Also, T_g recovery is observed upon removal of water by desorption.

erature. It is interesting that the reduction in T_g is 86 °C for saturated specimens immersed in water at 45 °C, whereas the drop in T_g is 49 °C for saturated specimens immersed in water at 90 °C. It is also noted that T_g increases with increasing bath temperature. This is exhibited in Table II and Fig. 5. This increase in T_g reflects the difference in the bonding nature and water interaction in the matrix phase of the composite. Studies have suggested [15,16] that water sorption in epoxies can be classified by three types. The sorbed water is partitioned as (i) Θ -bonded water which is water that is trapped in crack, flaws, delamination, voids, etc., as (ii) Λ -bonded water which is absorbed into the matrix and disrupts interchain existing hydrogen bond in the materials, and, as (iii) Γ -bonded water which reacts with hydrophilic functional groups of the main-chain molecules in the resin. It is suggested that Γ -bonded water forms somewhat stronger bond than those bonds formed by either Θ -bonded water or Λ -bonded water [15,16]. Γ -bonded water is believed to promote secondary cross linking thus enhancing the primary cross link density which increased T_g for high temperature immersion. Λ -bonded water tends to increase interchain mobility. Λ -bonded water, intrinsically, causes T_g to decrease and plasticization and swelling to increase. Θ -bonded water is retained at surfaces of crack tip, voids and other such flaws and, as such, does not interact chemically with the resin. Θ -bonded water is related more to surface tension and capillary type phenomena.

3.1.2.3 Water Desorption

The bonding tenacity of Θ -bonded, Λ -bonded and Γ -bonded water is demonstrated by desorption experiments. Θ -bonded water rapidly egresses upon desorption which suggests very weak bonding interaction with the matrix material. In contrast, Λ -bonded and Γ -bonded water is much more difficult to desorb out of the matrix phase in the composite. The desorption profile is

Fig. 6. Water desorption rates. Θ -bonded water and Λ -bonded water are more easily removed from the matrix by desorption than is Γ -bonded water.

exhibited in Fig. 6. From the desorption profile, the Θ -bonded water is lost extremely fast and accounts for 50% weight lost (water content loss) in a matter of a few hours at 60 °C. In contrast, the removal of Λ -bonded water reached a desorption plateau after about a 1000 h at 60 °C with

about 0.5 wt% sorbed water still remaining in the matrix. To expel the rest of the retained water in an expediently, the desorption temperature was raised to 100 °C and desorption which drove out Γ -bonded water continued for another 250 h. At this stage all the Γ -bonded water (so-called chemisorbed) water, was removed. A consequence of water expulsion from the composite, T_g recovers to its original, dry, as-received value. T_g recovery occurs regardless of prior hygrothermal conditioning (bath temperature). Because there is recovery of the T_g , one is compelled to ask the question concerning whether there is recovery of other physical and mechanical properties in the composite materials as well upon redrying. There is some indication that recovery of matrix-dominated mechanical properties is possible [16].

Fig. 7. (a) The effect of water sorption on delamination fracture toughness of graphite thermoplastic and graphite epoxy composites is exhibited after long-time exposure. b) The degree of change of delamination fracture toughness is shown for graphite thermoplastic and graphite epoxy composites. DFT for the thermoplastic is unaffected by long-time exposure to distilled water environment.

3.3 Fracture

As indicated in Fig. 7, sorbed moisture degrades the delamination fracture toughness (DFT) in thermoset composite laminates. A significant reduction in delamination fracture toughness occurred with moisture sorption under severe hygrothermal conditions. The extent of reduction in mode I delamination fracture toughness is approximately 60% following hygrothermal exposure of the graphite epoxy laminate for 1.3×10^7 s.

In Figs. 7a and 7b, the variation of DFT with moisture exposure time is exhibited. Clearly, moisture sorption has a more severe degrading effect on fracture toughness of graphite epoxy laminate, whereas moisture absorption has virtually no effect on DFT for fiber reinforced graphite thermoplastic composites. As evident in Figs. 7a and 7b, the influence of sorbed moisture on DFT for PEEK thermoplastic composites is insignificant. Several studies [11,17] have shown that the fracture toughness of graphite/PEEK thermoplastics is unaffected by moisture sorption. The marked difference in moisture-induced DFT between thermoset and thermoplastic composites is attributed partially to the fact that thermoset polymer matrix composites absorb substantially more moisture than thermoplastic polymer matrix composites do. As a result, moisture induced plasticization of the matrix and interfacial region is more severe for thermoset matrix composites. The moisture saturation level, M_m , for graphite/PEEK is $\sim 0.2\%$ whereas for graphite/epoxy laminates M_m can approach values somewhat larger than 2% by weight. Absorption of moisture in Gr/Ep laminates is about 10 times greater than in Gr/Tp laminates. Obviously, the maximum moisture content will depend on other factors such as fiber volume fraction, void content, residual stress, and polymer composition. Nonetheless, M_m for thermoplastics laminates is considerably less.

Morgan [18,19] and others [11,12,20,21] have reported on the degrading effects of moisture on physical and mechanical properties of thermoset polymers. Among these effects is that

moisture lowers the tensile strength, elongation and modulus of epoxy. Also, sorbed moisture tended to enhance the susceptibility of the matrix to cavitation and plastic flow processes. Preferential cracking along the fiber/matrix interface is exhibited in Figs. 8a and 8b for a graphite epoxy laminate exposed to hygrothermal conditions. Examination of the crack tip region shows major cracking in the interfacial region and microcrack link up of the inter-matrix region with interfacial cracking.

Fig. 8. (a) Fracture in the crack tip region of a graphite epoxy composite fracture specimen which has been exposed to moisture. Fracture is predominately along the fiber/matrix interface. (b) Fracture between the fiber/matrix interface is clearly illustrated. Interfacial decohesion is apparently the dominate failure mode in the composite as a result of moisture induced plasticization of the matrix material.

4.0 CONCLUSIONS

1. Water sorption in graphite epoxy (T300/934) exhibited both Fickian and non-Fickian diffusion behavior. Diffusion data showed time for the onset of non-Fickian behavior was inverse related to the exposure temperature. Non-Fickian behavior in the composite resulted because of chemical modification and physical damage to graphite epoxy material. The sorption of water in graphite thermoplastic (IM6/PEEK) material was generally Fickian.
2. T_g is reduced significantly with increasing moisture content. However, T_g increases slightly as the bath (immersion) temperature increases. It is suggested that this is due to secondary cross linking in the polymer. Upon moisture desorption, T_g recovers to its as-received, dry value for the composite material.
3. The delamination fracture toughness of graphite epoxy was reduced significantly due to the absorption of moisture. Sorbed moisture had no affect the delamination fracture toughness of graphite thermoplastic materials.

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